

Implementation of the Triple-D Model at BH Lim Special Needs Consultancy

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Abstract

This short paper touches on the author's learning journey in her modest attempt to provide her understanding of the Triple-D Model (Wong, Chia, & Lim, 2015) and its application with her four-year-old client at her workplace, an educational therapy center that provides intervention for young children, school-age children and adolescents. It explores the four phases involved in the application of the Triple-D Model of case management process in educational therapy: Phase 1-Diagnostics, Phase 2-Dialogics, Phase 3-Transition from Dialogics to Didactics, and Phase 4-Didactics. The final phase brings the readers back to the first phase of Diagnostics where it involves the evaluation of the intervention program and also provides feedback to the stakeholders (i.e., the client, the client's caregiver or parents, and the therapists) in the second phase of Dialogics. In this way, the treatment program designed to meet the client's needs could be further improved and adapted if it is to continue.

Keywords: Case management, Diagnostics, Dialogics, Didactics, Triple-D model

Introduction

In this paper, I will attempt to describe how the Triple-D Model is being implemented at BH Lim Special Needs Consultancy (BHLSNC). I will also attempt to explain the Triple-D Model with reference to a client (anonymously designated TYF), a four-year old boy currently attending the intervention program at BHLSNC.

In the educational therapy, a well-planned case management system (CMS) is an important aspect to consider in meeting the needs of the clients and leading them to a better outcome (see Liu, Xie, & Deng, 2023, for detail). First of all, what is CMS? According to NYS Promise (2018, p. 1:1), CMS is a fundamental intervention service that helps individuals gain access to essential services needed to achieve beneficial community living and learning outcomes. Therefore, a case manager who uses a structured CMS might help in establishing an intervention plan, tracking the client's progress, as well as promoting collaboration between therapists and parents that meets the needs of the client.

In CMS, a case manager will be involved in providing support services to the clients and families such as assisting them in determining individualized service plans, providing emotional support, and facilitating collaboration with community organizations and systems (NYS Promise, 2018, p. 1:9). Hence, the roles of a case manager would include monitoring the whole process of the service, being a support service coordinator, being a family/peer mentor, and a resource coordinator for specialized services (Wong, Chia, & Lim, 2015). Due to BHLSNC's limited human resources, the therapist will also serve as the case manager in providing feedback and adequate support to clients and families, as well as providing information and referrals for specialized services such as speech and language therapy (SLT) and occupational therapy (OT).

At BHLSNC, the Triple-D CMS has been used as a guideline to manage a case to ensure effective support for the client. The Triple-D model includes Diagnostics, Dialogics, and Didactics (Chia & Kee, 2012). The client undergoes the Triple-D processes which are explained in the next section as follows.

The Triple-D Model

The Triple-D model, introduced by Wong, Chia, and Lim (2015), is a framework used in special education case management. It comprises three key components: Diagnostics, Dialogics and Didactics.

❖ Diagnostics

According to Wong, Chia, & Lim (2015), educational diagnostics (a term coined and used by Li, Xie, & Deng, 2023) is a process that includes screening (evidence-based psychoeducational assessments), evaluation, and profiling of a client who may be facing learning and/or behavioral challenges. In other words, this first phase involves assessing the needs, abilities, and challenges of the student. It focuses on understanding the specific learning profile, strengths, weaknesses, and any disabilities or exceptionalities. The steps involved in the Diagnostic phase (case measurement) include the following:

Step 1:

A screening assessment is conducted on a client who is suspected to have learning and/or behavioral challenges to identify the client's strengths, challenges, learning styles, and preferences. In TYF's case, an evidence-based assessment, Ages & Stages Questionnaires[®]-Third Edition (ASQ-3[™]; Squires & Bricker, 2009) was used. This is a screening process for young children aged between 1 to 66 months for developmental delays in five areas: communication, gross motor, fine motor, problem solving, and personal social (see Squires & Bricker, 2009, for detail). Alongside the ASQ-3[™] (Squires & Bricker, 2009), the companion Ages & Stages Questionnaires[®]-Socio-Emotional-Second Edition (ASQ[®]:SE-2; Squires, Bricker, & Twombly, 2015) was also used. This is to screen a child between 0 to 72 months in seven behavioral areas: self-regulation, compliance, communication, adaptive functioning, autonomy, affect, and interaction with people (Squires, Bricker, & Twombly, 2002, 2015).

As TYF engaged with the therapists (clinical observation phase) in interactive and stipulated activities, TYF's mother and grandmother responded to the ASQ-3[™] (Squires & Bricker, 2009) and ASQ[®]:SE-2 (Squires, Bricker, & Twombly, 2002, 2015) interview schedules. The outcomes of TYF's ASQ-3[™] scores indicated that he was below the cut-off in communication, fine motor, problem solving, and personal-social. This suggests that TYF's development is delayed in these four areas. Whilst gross motor was above the cut-off, it was in the *monitoring* zone. According to the Educator's Diagnostic Manual of Disabilities and Disorders (EDM; Pierangelo & Guiliani, 2007), TYF is said to have Global Developmental Delay (GDD). This indicates that TYF has failed to achieve developmental milestones in a few areas of intellectual functioning (see Pierangelo & Guliani, 2007, for more detail). In the ASQ[®]:SE-2, TYF was found to be *at-risk* for developing social-emotional issues. The outcomes of the assessment, corroborated by feedback from family members, and a close-up observation of his behavior, provide triangulated data that TYF manifests many traits suggestive of autism spectrum condition (ASC), which should not be mistaken for autism spectrum disorder (ASD).

Step 2:

In step 2, diagnostic tests based on the hierarchy of abilities and skills (innate abilities, sensory perceptuo-motor skills and abilities, adaptive behavioral skills and abilities, socio-emotional behavioral skills and abilities, and cognitive skills and abilities) are administered (Wong, Chia, & Lim, 2015).

In TYF's case, these diagnostic tests were not administered because of parents expressed financial difficulties. Absence of such essential data from the diagnostic evaluation has important implications for the therapists attempting to construct an Individualized Education Plan (IEP) appropriate to TYF's needs. Fortunately, however, as soon as financial subsidy became available for TYF, the Sensory Profile Caregiver Questionnaire (SP-CQ; Dunn, 1999) and Gilliam Autism Rating Scale-3rd Edition (GARS-3; Gilliam, 2006) were administered.

Step 3:

In this step, outcomes from the psychoeducational assessments are analyzed to have a good understanding of the client's strengths and areas of need. In TYF's case, outcomes from the assessments

suggest that TYF has gross motor skills on par with his same-age peers, but he has significant delays in the areas of communication, fine motor, problem solving, and personal-social skills.

❖ Dialogics

Dialogics may be defined as the process by which communicative parties attain mutual agreement on purposeful communication by verifying each other's perceived viewpoint and contextual understanding, perceived use, and relationship of conveyed ideas and perceived meanings (Bakhtin, 1939, as cited in Todorov, 1984). In other words, this second phase emphasizes collaboration and communication among stakeholders involved in the student's education. It encourages open dialogue between educators, parents, specialists, and the student to develop a comprehensive plan that addresses the individual's needs. Steps involved in the Dialogics phase (case consultation) include the following:

Step 1:

In step 1 of the Dialogics or Educational Dialogics (Liu, Xie, & Deng, 2023) phase, the client's parents collaborate with other professionals who understand the client's condition to form a Case Management Team (CMT) to support the client throughout the intervention period. Such a consultative team aims to confirm the assessment results and identifies the key personnel who will be actively involved in assisting the client throughout the intervention period (Wong, Chia, & Lim, 2015).

Going back to TYF's case, an earlier initial consultation had been conducted with members of the family to better understand TYF's first three years of life (including prenatal and postnatal information), and specific developmental milestones achieved. Family members were also asked about their concerns about TYF's development, and what their main goals were in referring TYF to BHLSNC.

Family members reported that TYF currently attends a typical kindergarten with a weekly (hourly) one-on-one additional session. TYF was also attending weekly OT sessions which his mom eventually terminated as she felt TYF was not benefiting from these sessions. However, it was not possible to obtain a report from the OT.

Further attempts to obtain more information from the OT center have not been fruitful. On reflection, attempts to "dialogue" with other allied fields in special needs education have been challenging due to a number of factors. First, the scarcity of services creates competition among service providers; second, service providers are often concerned about guarding over their area of "speciality". These factors seriously hinder collaboration and dialogue among the various disciplines, with the eventual "loser" being the special needs client.

Hence in the current situation, TYF's family members constitute the key personnel providing support and feedback about his progress. Apart from the brief verbal report (the family also receives a Session Intervention Report via *WhatsApp*) with family members after each intervention session, a quarterly family conference has been arranged to provide on-going feedback and review of TYF's IEP.

Step 2:

In this step, the CMT needs to decide whether the client should continue with the CM support service or be referred to other specialized services to ensure the service provided to the client who requires the most vital service (Wong, Chia, & Lim, 2015). Some resources, such as subsidies and referral systems should be provided to the client's family to help them make the best decision on selecting the next support service provider.

In TYF's case, the family decided to continue with the CM support service. Additional financial subsidy was sought to enable TYF to continue with the intervention services. The family was also recommended to seek Speech Language Therapy (SLT) services, but this was not taken up because earlier SLT services did not seem to benefit TYF.

❖ Transition from Dialogics to Didactics

This transition phase involves constructing the IEP for the client. The Triple-T Model of Learning is used to identify and understand how to assist clients in learning from the pedagogical perspectives (Chia & Kee, 2013; also see Wong, Chia, & Lim, 2015, for more detail). The Triple-T Model includes *Epistēmē* (what of learning), *Telos* (why of learning), and *Technē* (how of learning). The transition phase is also known as case development, case planning, or case building (Wong, Chia, & Lim, 2015).

In the “what of learning”, the Carolina Curriculum for Pre-schoolers with Special Needs, 2nd Edition. (CCPSN; Johnson-Martin, Attermeier, & Hacker, 2004), was used to guide the construction of TYF’s IEP appropriate to his developmental level.

The CCPSN (Johnson-Martin, Attermeier, & Hacker, 2004) is designed for young children who have mild to severe disabilities between the age of 24 to 60 months with 22 teaching sequences covering five developmental domains such as personal-social, cognition, communication, fine motor, and gross motor (Johnson-Martin et.al, 2004). The CCPSN evaluates the client’s performance based on 4 legends (able to do independently, able to do with verbal prompting, able to do with physical prompting, unable or refuse to do) (see Johnson-Martin, Attermeier, & Hacker, 2004, for detail). TYF’s IEP was guided by outcomes from the ASQ-3™ assessment (Squires & Bricker, 2009). Figure 1 below illustrates the short-term objectives in CCPSN (Johnson-Martin, Attermeier, & Hacker, 2004), visual perception: blocks and puzzles.

Cognition	
6-I. Visual Perception: Blocks & Puzzles	
Age (mths)	Curriculum Sequences
24-30	a. Places round, square, and triangular forms in reversed form board
	b. Imitates block train
30-36	c. Puts together two-piece puzzles
	d. Imitates block building
	e. Imitates block bridge
	f. Puts together puzzle with four or five interconnected pieces
36-42	g. Imitates horizontal (flat on the table) block patterns of two and three blocks (two colors)
42-48	h. Imitates horizontal block patterns of four to six blocks (two colors)
	i. Completes 8- to 12- pieces interconnected puzzles
48-54	j. Imitates construction of a simple visual pattern using parquetry blocks
	k. Builds representationally with blocks
54-60	l. Completes 15- to 25- piece interconnected puzzles
	m. Reproduces simple block designs from memory

Figure 1. Visual Perception: Blocks & Puzzles

Each intervention session conducted, usually involving more than one therapists using multi-sensory methods. Tools used usually combine two or more senses such as see (sight), touch (tactile), hear (auditory), smell (olfactory), taste, and movement (kinesthetics). Being an active child, TYF prefers hands-on activities. Talk tools have been included in the intervention session to help TYF develop oral motor skills.

In constructing the IEP, CMT looks at the annual objectives, short-term objectives, and behavioral objectives. The annual objectives are the long-term goals to be achieved by the client. Short-term objectives are developed and expanded from the annual objectives with a stipulated time frame, for example, 3 months. The behavioral objectives are developed and expanded from the short-term objectives. Behavioral objectives based on the CCPSN are carefully selected based on TYF’s current developmental level, that is, not too difficult to avoid frustration, and yet not too easy so that TYF will be challenged to improve. Figure 2 below shows the objectives selected for TYF based on the CCPSN.

<p>Annual Objective: Cognition</p> <p><i>Short Term Objective: 6-I. Visual Perception: Blocks & Puzzles</i></p> <p><i>Behavioural Objective:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. a. Places round, square, and triangular forms in reversed form board 2. b. Imitates block train 3. c. Puts together two-piece puzzles
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Figure 2. Annual, Short-Term, and Behavioral Objectives in TYF’s IEP

❖ **Didactics**

Didactics - also known as Educational Didactics (Liu, Xie, & Deng, 2023) - could be defined as having the ability to teach the content knowledge by implementing different teaching aids and methods to help the client to learn (Gundem, 1998, p. 19-24, as cited in Wong, Chia, & Lim, 2015). In other words, once the assessment is completed and dialogue established, this phase focuses on implementing tailored instructional strategies and interventions. It aims to deliver effective teaching methods and support systems that cater to the student’s unique learning requirements. Steps involved in the didactics phase (case intervention or case treatment) include:

Step 1:

The IEP will be implemented over a period of time negotiated by CMT in consultation with TYF’s family.

In the course of intervention, if TYF achieves independence in a behavioral objective, his IEP will be upgraded accordingly. At BHLSNC, a client is required to attend at least 2 intervention sessions per week, each session lasting one hour. Each intervention session is documented on a Session Intervention Record (SIR), and sent to TYF’s family for their keeping. An example of the SIR is shown in Figure 3.

Cognition				
6-I. Visual Perception: Blocks & Puzzles	I	VP	PP	X
c. TYF is able to put together two-piece puzzles.				
<u>Suggested activity:-</u>				
- <i>Playing with animal wooden puzzle. (Remark: TYF seemed confused with the orientation of the puzzle pieces. He appeared to have some difficulties in rotating the puzzle to match the shape.)</i>			/	

Figure 3. Example of an SIR

Step 2:

Here, the client’s progress is monitored to make necessary referrals to other consultants, or to implement more appropriate strategies to support the client.

At BHLSNC, SIRs are carefully compiled and reviewed every three months. Behavioral objectives are expected to change over time depending on the client’s progress. A parent conference is conducted on a quarterly basis. During the parent conference, a quarterly IEP review is presented, and parents are encouraged to provide their feedback. Therapists working with the client report on the progress (or lack thereof) in specific areas and suggest appropriate changes. This is done in consultation with the parents, who at this conference have the option to continue (or discontinue) with the intervention sessions. Should parents opt to continue with the intervention, the conference will attempt to decide on the appropriate objectives to construct the IEP for the following quarter. Figure 4 shows an example of the Quarterly IEP Evaluation Report.

<p>Cognition</p> <p>6-1. Visual Perception: Blocks & Puzzles</p> <p>c. Puts together two-piece puzzles (30-36 mths)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires PP - TYF was confused with the orientation of the puzzle pieces; he has difficulty in rotating puzzle to match the shape

Figure 4. Example item in the Quarterly IEP Evaluation Report

Step 3:

This step is carried out before the eventual “discharge” of the client. Outcomes from the intervention sessions are collected for systematic analysis and compared to the results obtained from the assessment done in the Diagnostics phase. Such a *pre-* and *post-* analysis helps to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention carried out.

Of course, TYF has yet to come to this stage. At BHLSNC, the client is re-screened using both ASQ-3™ (Squires & Bricker, 2009) and ASQ®:SE-2 (Squires, Bricker, & Twombly, 2002, 2015). Outcomes of this re-screen are compared to the initial outcomes carried out before commencement of early intervention to gauge the client’s progress.

Upon discharge, the client often transitions to another setting, such as a school. BHLSNC proactively supports this transition process, which usually involves the CM keeping in close contact with the client’s family, and other personnel in the new setting.

Conclusion

So, how useful has the Triple-D Model been at BHLSNC? After working with BHLSNC for more than a year, I venture to say that this model provides a clear and systematic guide for negotiating through the many challenging situations as I attempt to support my client with special needs. Reflecting on the Triple-D Model and its application at BHLSNC has helped me identify a number of limitations.

With regards to the first “D” (Diagnostics), I have come to realize that many clients do not have proper diagnosis. Some families do not seek formal diagnosis because of the fees involved; yet others are in denial, hoping their child will outgrow their difficulties, and so do not seek help much earlier. Some have attended months of SLT and/or OT services (as in the case of TYF) but were not given reports of progress.

As for the second “D” (Dialogics), there seems to be little opportunities for the professionals to consult each other. I wonder if the scarcity of services in the area of special needs has made service providers especially competitive, so that professionals hold back from sharing their knowledge. Sadly, it is the special needs client who loses out if professionals are reluctant to “dialogue” with each other.

In the final “D” (Didactics), I realize the need for more trained personnel in the field. There is a real need for persons who are trained to understand diagnostic reports, interpret them, and to put together a *Case Review Report* that accurately reflects the psycho-educational and diagnostic profile of the special needs client, before even attempting to put together an IEP that can help the client effectively.

In view of all the above, I am truly thankful to be enrolled on the Special Needs Educational Therapy (SNET) course under the auspices of the International Association of Counselors and Therapists (IACT). This has given me the opportunity to reflect on my role in BHLSNC, specifically in applying the Triple-D Model as I learn to manage the case of TYF.

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